

THE ESSENTIAL FEATURES OF CLT APPROACH IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract

This article explores the key characteristics of the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in educating and improving English language skills of learners. Key characteristics featured include the CLT's goal, classroom activities, and teachers and students' roles. In the process of this study, internationally published normative-legal documents, academic and scientific-theoretical manuals and literature on the history and practice of CLT have been used in order to analyse the English teaching and learning context. It has been found that the shift from previously dominant methods such as Grammar-Translation Methods to CLT has not only been welcomed by teachers and learners, but also has caused some criticisms by some scholars in the fields of linguistics and language teaching.

Keywords: CLT, GTM, communicative competence, grammatical competence

1. Introduction

In the world today, learning English has become a vital tool for global communication among the world nations. It is taught as lingua franca at many levels of education in lots of countries. Obviously, there has risen an enormous global need for quality English language teaching and English language teaching materials and resources. This is because global demand for language acquisition requires people to easily engage in communication and be able to enter into meaningful interaction with both native and non-native speakers of English. Therefore, in the language teaching and learning nowadays CLT is the most common approach that are being employed for that purpose. According to Chiesa et al. (2019), "CLT's relevance to the language curriculum is paramount. The CLT shifted the focus from grammar mastery to a communicative one, which implies change in approaches and attitudes towards the goal of teaching, the teacher and learner roles, and the nature of interaction amongst learners." Before the CLT approach, a variety of language teaching methods has been in use. However, one should not understand that we have to abolish traditional ways of teaching, rather use CLT to adapt instructional resources to improve communicative competence of our students.

2. Main Part

Many English language teachers at present favour the methodology which they call "communicative" as the methodology of choice. However, when asked to give a detailed description of what they mean by "communicative," explanations vary widely. So, there are several questions that arise here. Does CLT mean teaching conversation, an absence of grammar in a course, or an emphasis on open-ended discussion activities as the main features of a course? Thus, CLT can be understood as a set of principles about the goals of language teaching, how learners learn the language, the kinds of classroom activities that best facilitate learning, the roles of teachers and learners in the classroom (Richards, 2006)

2.1 The CLT Goal

The goal of CLT is teaching communicative competence. To understand what this means, it seems better to compare it with the concept of grammatical competence. Grammatical competence is the knowledge about a language that accounts for our ability to produce sentences in a language. It refers to knowledge of the building blocks of sentences (e.g., parts of speech, tenses, phrases, clauses, sentence patterns) and how sentences are formed. Grammatical competence being the focus of many grammar practice books, which typically present a rule of grammar on one page, and provide exercises to practice using the rule on the other, is an important dimension of language learning. Nevertheless, it is clearly not all that is involved in learning a language since one can master the rules of sentence formation in a language and still not be very successful at being able to use the language for meaningful communication. It is the latter capacity which is understood by the term communicative competence. Thus, the outputs of communicative competence enable learners to be able to use the language for various purposes and functions, skilfully apply language skills in formal and informal contexts, produce and comprehend different text types, and maintain communication despite having knowledge limitations (Richards, 2006).

2.2 How Learners Learn the Language

In theory, CLT or the communicative approach is an approach to language teaching that emphasizes interaction as both the means and the ultimate goal of study. Language learners in environments utilizing CLT techniques, learn and practice the target language through the interaction with one another and the instructor, the study of “authentic texts” (those written in the target language for purposes other than language learning), and through the use of the language both in class and outside of class. Learners converse about personal experiences with partners, and instructors teach topics outside of the realm of traditional grammar, in order to promote language skills in all types of situations. This method also claims to encourage learners to incorporate their personal experiences into their language learning environment, and to focus on the learning experience in addition to the learning of the target language. Accordingly, the students learn how to learn, and as a result, they take responsibility for their own learning.

2.3 CLT Classroom Activities

In CLT, students get input by listening and reading (receptive skill), and there will be interaction among them to execute the information or the material and finally, they will give an output in speaking or writing (productive skill). It means CLT can cover all the language skills and grammar will be taught implicit. In CLT, the material is designed to train the analytical and critical thinking of the learners, so it will improve their English skill not only the language itself but also to use the language in various functions and purposes. In the classroom, CLT often takes the type of pair and group work requiring negotiation and cooperation between/among learners. The activities that are used in CLT can include role play, interview, surveys, games and many more that will stimulate the learners to be more active. To this point, I think CLT is a really good one for teacher to use, because it can train all language skills and improve learners' analytical and critical thinking and their knowledge will increase just by learning language using this approach.

2.4 Teacher vs Student Roles in CLT

According to Deckert, based on student centeredness, the CLT requires low profile teacher roles, constant pair work or small group problem solving, students responding to authentic texts, extended exchanges on versatile topics, and the implementation of the four basic skills, namely speaking, listening, reading, and writing. The CLT discourages teacher centeredness, quizzing of memorized material, and detailed commentary on forms of English. Consequently, CLT often

demands teachers to use less teacher-centred activities and skills. Instructors are responsible for organizing the classroom as a setting for communication and communicative activities. In addition, CLT activities have shifted language classrooms' focus from the function and the teacher to the learner.

In CLT, the goal of language education is the ability to communicate in the target language (Savignon, 1997). This is in contrast to previous views in which grammatical competence was commonly given top priority (Bax, 2003). CLT also focuses on the teacher being a facilitator, rather than an instructor. Students are actively involved in interpretation, expression and negotiation of meaning. Accordingly, the teacher is an analyst and task designer whereas the students are improvisers and negotiators. Moreover, it is crucial for the teachers to correct the learners' mistakes immediately. Otherwise, once the wrong patterns and rules become fixed in students' minds, then they will result in habits difficult to change, and accuracy is therefore much more emphasized than fluency. If learners make errors during speaking, the errors are tolerated in order to encourage fluency.

However, it does not mean that errors are ignored and the teacher may not give learners feedback. Error correction should be applied during teaching rather than while students are practising in the target language. Otherwise, it causes a permanent habit in which students hesitate every time they use the target language.

In the more creative types of activity, teachers should avoid unnecessary intervention because this may prevent learners from becoming involved with the activity and developing their communicative skills. The teachers' function becomes less dominant, but no less important in some situations. Teachers may find themselves talking less and listening more, becoming active facilitators of their students' learning and facilitating communication in the classroom. In speaking practice, it is the students' turn to do most of the talking. The teachers are like the skilful conductor of an orchestra, giving each of the performers a chance to participate and monitoring their performance to see that it is satisfactory.

Unlike traditional and teacher-centred approaches, CLT is against the teacher dominance in the classroom and supports a more equal relationship among the teachers and the students. The CLT teacher assumes a responsibility for determining and responding to learner language needs. The teacher is the manager of classroom activities. In this role, one of his major responsibilities is to establish situations likely to promote communication. A classroom during a communicative activity is far from quiet; therefore, the teacher has to be aware of classroom management issues.

2.5 Criticism of CLT

Although CLT has been extremely influential in the field of language teaching, it is not universally accepted and has been subject to significant critique. It was Swan who criticised its theoretical and practical aspects proposing that there was a great mismatch between the understandings of CLT by linguists and language teachers. He claimed that CLT theory could lead to confusion in the application of CLT techniques in classroom settings (Swan, 1985).

Further critique of CLT techniques in classroom teaching can be attributed to Elaine Ridge who mentions that the generally agreed upon consensus regarding the definition of "communicative competence" are not justified in practice. Because there is not such agreement, students may be seen to be in possession of "communicative competence" without being able to make full, or even adequate, use of the language. That an individual is proficient in a language does not necessarily entail that they can make full use of that language, which can limit an individual's potential with

that language, especially if that language is an endangered language. This critique is largely to do with the fact that CLT is often highly praised and is popular, when it may not necessarily be the best method of language teaching. Ridge also notes that CLT has nonspecific requirements of its teachers as there is no completely standard definition of what CLT is; this is especially true for the teaching of grammar. Some critics of CLT suggest that the method does not put enough emphasis on the teaching of grammar and instead allows students to produce utterances which are grammatically incorrect as long as the interlocutor can get some meaning from them (Ridge, 1992).

Stephen Bax's critique of CLT has to do with the context of its implementation. Bax asserts that many researchers associate the use of CLT techniques with modernity and, therefore, the lack of CLT techniques as a lack of modernism. In this way, these researchers consider teachers or school systems which don't use CLT techniques as outdated and suggest that their students learn the target language "in spite of" the absence of CLT techniques, as though CLT were the only way to learn a language and everyone who fails to implement its techniques is ignorant and will not be successful in teaching the target language (Bax, 2003).

3. Conclusion

CLT has attained a dominant approach throughout the world. It is believed that this approach has strengthened teaching and learning process because of its focus on the power of communication (Al-Amri, 2018). Communication is viewed as the source of learning and is the medium of teaching. However, CLT approach should not be taken for granted as the main tool for learning the language. It is erroneously believed that if learners are communicating, they must be learning and such a belief can be harmful. Many teachers assume that all they need to do is to set communicative activities in the classroom to enable learning to take place. This results that the learner's attention is focused on meaning rather than linguistic structure. CLT has changed the way English is taught. It most of the time involves the use of pair work activities, role plays, group work activities and project works. In CLT activities, students are supposed to interact with each other through the group work activities, which allows the students to be exposed to purposeful and authentic language use rather than mechanical practice of language drills. In this way, CLT is a perfect approach to teaching and learning a language as it was cited by Bax (2003). It must be noted that no perfect approach to learning and teaching exists. But CLT approach could be improved considering the whole context and thus assessment and language structure should get more attention. So, learners' needs, motivation, context, cultures, and grammar should be carefully considered in regard to using CLT and development of communicative competence of learners. The EFL learner has to learn rules of communication as well as rules of grammar. Fotos (2003) suggests that instead of favouring one method over the other, grammar teaching and communicative activities should be combined to achieve teaching goals. Therefore, a mix of grammar, context, and CLT approaches can be a useful method for achieving the desired level of language learning and teaching. Thus, teachers and students' roles in class activities make up the critical focus of communicative teaching. Most of the negative and fruitless examples were observed to have been resulted from either the teachers or students' lack of organisation and implication of CLT. Teachers' language competence and creative ability primarily affect the final product. How they understand the CLT, how they instruct the students, and how much intervention is necessary determine their roles and the outcome of their performance.

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TECHNIQUES AND METHODS OF TEACHING READING SKILLS TO INTERMEDIATE LEVEL OF LEARNERS

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Abstract

The article deals with the techniques and methods of teaching reading skills to intermediate level of learners. The purpose of this article is to assist educators in teaching reading significant difficulties. The article provides a general description of reading methods and techniques.

Key words: techniques, methods, reading, intermediate, comprehension, text and pictures.

It is important to know how to teach reading to the learners. Teachers should adopt the appropriate technique considering previous performance of the learners, their linguistic level, ability to perceive new items or vocabulary etc.

It has been already stated that meaning of a text is not 'inherent'. It is the reader who brings meaning with him/her. For this reason, the same text can be interpreted in different ways though the writer may have only one idea while writing the text. For this reason, learners should be taught how to reach the proper meaning of the text. If they fail to guess or comprehend the meaning a text implies, all the efforts and techniques to teach reading to the learners will end in smoke.

It is now obvious that the teaching of meaning is the most important task for the teacher. Text-based outlook of the learners should be changed. Learners should be trained properly so that they may be able to associate the textual meaning to their experience. According to Dechant (1982: 37) "Proficient readers are those who... have an adequate knowledge base that allows them to bring meaning to the printed page." So, proper association between the textual words and the experience or knowledge is essential for a better comprehending. Meaning can be associated with the printed word only by associating the word with the experience, whether real or vicarious, or by associating it with another symbol which fits the context.

As meaning starts its operation from the 'word', it is suggested to give importance on 'word knowledge', as "word knowledge is the most important factor for reading comprehension or for reading with meaning in the elementary and secondary school years" (op. cit. p. 288). Dechant has suggested 'a threefold process' for the 'teaching of meaning for the words':

- Learners should be taught the basic or 'literal meaning' of words.
- They should be taught what the other alternatives of a particular word are synonyms, for example.
- And they should know how a particular word for a particular purpose can be used fitting the context.

The overall meaning of a text can be taught through DRA (Directed Reading Activity) suggested by Dechant. According to him (p. 292) basic steps of the DRA are:

